

TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED ON FREE-STANDING TEXTILE FORMWORK

Martin Scheurer, Institut für Textiltechnik, RWTH Aachen University, Germany,

martin.scheuer@ita.rwth-aachen.de

Tobias Neef, Institute of Construction Materials, Technical University Dresden, Germany,

tobias.neef@tu-dresden.de

Gözdem Dittel, Institut für Textiltechnik, RWTH Aachen University, Germany,

goezdem.dittel@ita.rwth-aachen.de

Viktor Mechtcherine, Institute of Construction Materials, Technical University Dresden, Germany,

mechtcherine@tu-dresden.de

Thomas Gries, Institut für Textiltechnik, RWTH Aachen University, Germany,

thomas.gries@ita.rwth-aachen.de

ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing and textile reinforced concrete (TRC) are both highly topical research areas for the construction industry, both offering novel solutions to pressing problems of the industry. By combining the new material TRC with additive manufacturing methods, the advantages of both are kept and weaknesses eliminated. The authors propose a combination of TRC and additive manufacturing by utilizing a multi layered textile fixed in place at a few supporting points and printing concrete into and onto this textile formwork. Thereby, shell like structures can be produced using 3D concrete printing. Initial production trials demonstrate the viability of the proposed method.

KEYWORDS

additive manufacturing; textile reinforced concrete; integrated formwork; digital concrete; carbon reinforced concrete

INTRODUCTION

The process innovation of additive manufacturing (AM) with concrete and the material innovation of textile reinforced concrete (TRC) are two highly topical areas of research promising solutions for some of the most pressing challenges of the global construction industry. The two biggest advantages of AM are a drastic decrease of necessary manual labor on the construction site by increasing automation and material savings by eliminating the need for a formwork while still enabling complex geometries (Buswell et al., 2022; Mechtcherine et al., 2021). These advantages tackle two of the major challenges of the construction industry, namely labour shortage and large material use. AM of concrete structures has made major advances in the last years, with first commercial projects being completed, but several challenges still remain. Two of these challenges are the integration of a reinforcement into the AM process and the production of overhanging or horizontal components (such as shell, beams, etc.) without shuttering.

TRC on the other hand is a material innovation in which the traditional steel reinforcement is replaced by a reinforcement made of high performance technical textiles (Friese et al., 2022). Since these textiles do not corrode when in contact with the environment, the necessary concrete thickness can be minimized to the structurally necessary amount, enabling thickness reductions and significant concrete savings (Beckmann et al., 2021). TRC therefore enables large material savings in the construction industry. The high load bearing capacity of the textiles and the low weight of TRC elements makes them ideally suited for slabs and shell structures (Osman-Letelier et al., 2021). However, currently, production of TRC elements requires trained manual labour for production. Additionally, while the high shapeability of the textiles enables complex geometries, current production methods require complex formworks for the realization of such geometries.

Within this paper, the authors propose the combination of the process innovation of AM with the material innovation of TRC. This approach enables the combination of the strengths of both approaches while mitigating their weaknesses. Several combinations of TRC and AM with concrete are currently being investigated in academia, ranging from the integration of reinforcement yarns into the concreting process to the addition of reinforcing textiles to the finished concrete structure. The authors propose a different approach, in which a textile is used for multiple purposes during the AM with concrete. The textile is used simultaneously as an integrated shuttering for the AM with concrete and as an internal reinforcement of the finished concrete element. This is done using a minimum of supporting structures and secondary work with a fully automated concreting process.

In this approach (see Figure 1), a multi-layered textile is fixed on as few tensioning and support points as possible and used to define the outer geometry of the element. The supporting structure is designed to be fully reusable. The bottom layer of the textile is constructed as a close meshed support structure fulfilling the role of integrated formwork and holding the concrete in place. The top layer of the textile is fulfilling the role of static minimum reinforcement and is fully penetrated by the concrete. Where necessary, the textile is further reinforced using additively placed reinforcing layers made of mineral impregnated carbon rovings (Mechtcherine et al., 2020; Schneider et al., 2019). The whole textile is covered additively with automatically placed concrete using a concrete extrusion printing head for a robot, using as little concrete as possible to create a shell structure. The added weight of the concrete leads to deformation of the textile, which is taken into account during the design of the support structures and can be used for the production of curved, complex shapes.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the proposed approach for the combination of AM and TRC

Within this paper, the authors present suitable textile structures and suitable concrete mixtures for the proposed approach and first results of production trials, demonstrating the viability of the approach.

TEXTILE STRUCTURE

As described above, the textile structure fulfils multiple roles within the proposed approach. The first role of the textile is acting as an integrated formwork, meaning that the textile should not be penetrated by the concrete and keep the concrete in the desired shape until it is cured and stable. The second role of the textile is to act as a static minimum reinforcement throughout the whole structure, carrying any bending and tensile loads. For this purpose, the textile needs to be integrated into the concrete to facilitate load induction. Since both roles require different textile designs, the use of a multi layered textile with each layer fulfilling one of the roles is evident. Separating the textile roles into two layers however requires the design of a connection between the layers to ensure that they are

spaced evenly throughout the whole element. In the following subchapters, the design of the two textile layers and the connection between the layers are discussed.

Support Layer

The use of textiles as formwork has been examined by several researchers. For example a knitted textile was used as an integrated formwork for their production of the KnitCandela concrete shell (Popescu et al., 2021). Other approaches used woven textiles or warp knitted non-crimp fabrics as textile formworks (Veenendaal et al., 2011). Based on this research and experiences in TRC, the authors propose the use of a close meshed warp-knitted non-crimp fabric for the formwork/support layer. Since the support layer in the proposed approach is not required to absorb large mechanical loads, the use of more economic materials, such as polymer or E-glass fibres, is suggested.

Reinforcement Layer

The use of textiles as reinforcement is the basic idea of TRC. Therefore, the extensive research in the field of TRC can be used as a guideline for the design of the textile reinforcement layer. The most common reinforcement textiles in TRC are warp-knitted biaxial non-crimp fabrics with grid like mesh openings (Friese et al., 2022). To ensure a sufficient reinforcement effect and to carry the mechanical loads, the use of high performance materials such as carbon or alkaline resistant glass fibres is suggested. In addition, since the textile needs to be shapeable to enable the production of curved shell structures, the commonly used polymer impregnation of the reinforcement textile needs to be omitted or only flexible polymer impregnation materials can be used.

Connection Between the Layers

The use of multiple layers of reinforcement is common practice in TRC and multiple solutions to connect these layers have already been developed. Those solutions can be adapted for the use in the proposed approach. The first solution for the connection of multiple layers established in TRC is the use of plastic spacer clips, which are connected to the textile layers at specific points and ensure the desired spacing between the layers of the textile at those points (Walther et al., 2014). A second solution is the use of an additional textile that is added in between the textile layers and which ensures the desired spacing between the layers across the whole textile area. This connecting textile can either be glued to the other two layers or simply be placed in between to be enclosed by the concrete matrix. The third solution is the use of so called 3D spacer fabrics, in which two layers of non-crimp fabrics are produced simultaneously and connected by pile threads, which ensure the precise spacing of the textile layers (Gries et al., 2022).

Proposed Textile Structures

Based on the design of the individual textile layers and the connection between the layers described above, three different textile structures are possible for the additive manufacturing of concrete on a free standing textile formwork, which mainly differ in the method of connection between the layers (cf. Figure 2). For all three textile structures, the support layer consists of a close meshed non-crimp fabric made of alkaline resistant glass rovings without any impregnation. The reinforcement layer consists of a grid-like biaxial non-crimp fabric made of carbon rovings, either without impregnation or with an impregnation made of flexible polymers to ensure the drapability of the textile. For the connection between the layers, all three possible solutions described above are viable and can therefore be analysed for the proposed approach.

Possible textile for the reinforcement layer

Open meshed, grid like carbon fibre textile

Possible textile for the support layer

Close meshed, grid like glass fibre textile

Possible solutions for the connection between the layers

Plastic spacer clips

Textile separation layer

Pile threads (3D spacer fabrics)

Figure 2: Possible textile structures for the reinforcement layer and support layer and possible solutions for the connection between the layers

For the initial trials presented in this paper, the first solution for connecting the layers using plastic spacers is used. The reinforcement layer consists of a grid like warp knitted fabric made of carbon/alkaline resistant glass. The support layer is similarly made from a warp-knitted fabric made of alkaline resistant glass rovings, but the grid opening is much more closed to limit the concrete penetration.

CONCRETE MIXTURE

AM with concrete places complex requirements on the concrete mixture. The concrete mixture must be pumpable to be delivered to the printing head via a hose (in case of this work with a diameter of 19 mm). At the extrusion nozzle, the concrete mixture needs to be extrudable to ensure geometric stability and good surface quality. In addition, good buildability is required if multiple layers are to be printed. The proposed approach in this paper adds two more requirements. First, the reinforcement layer needs to be penetrated and enclosed by the concrete matrix, and second, the support layer must not be penetrated.

Based on prior concrete mixtures and pre-trials, a concrete mix according to Table 1 was designed (Neef, Butler, & Mechtcherine, 2022; Neef, Müller, & Mechtcherine, 2022). This mixture was adjusted by varying the amount of superplasticizer to achieve the desired consistency and flow properties. The mix listed in Table 1 achieved a slump diameter of 17.5 cm, according to a flow test on the Haegermann-flow-table (HFT) after 15 strokes according to DIN EN 1015-3.

Table 1: Concrete mixture used in this paper

Ingredient	Microsilica fume	Ultra fine OPC	OPC I 42.5 R	Sand 0.06/0.2	Sand 0/1	Sand 0/2	Tap water	Super-plasticizer
Amount [kg/m ³]	12.5	353	299	205	330	710	279	6

INTERACTIONS BETWEEN TEXTILE AND CONCRETE

As previously mentioned, the flowability of fresh concrete is crucial to ensure its ability to encase the reinforcement layer effectively. This is demonstrated in Figure 3a, where a failed printing trial is depicted. The concrete material used in this case had a HFT value of 18.0 cm, indicating its stiff consistency. As a result, the concrete was unable to fully penetrate the reinforcement layer, which had a mesh size of 15 mm x 10 mm.

In Figure 3b, tests were conducted using concrete with a HFT value of 21.5 cm. This concrete consistency exhibited improved flowability, allowing it to neatly enclose the same textile used as the reinforcement layer. However, when a close-meshed glass fibre textile was used as the support layer, the concrete mixture was not able to penetrate through it, indicating a limitation in its viscosity.

To address this limitation, additional superplasticizer was added to the concrete mixture, resulting in an increased HFT value of 24.0 cm. This modification made the mixture excessively flowable, as shown in Figure 3c. Consequently, the concrete penetrated through the support textile, compromising its structural integrity.

Therefore, it is important to achieve an appropriate viscosity of the fresh concrete, which on the one hand is fluid enough to effectively envelop the reinforcement layer, but on the other hand avoids excessive flow, which can lead to undesired flow through the textile or penetration of the support layer.

Figure 3: Printing trial with different consistencies a) too stiff (HFT 18.0 cm) b) good (HFT 21.5 cm) c) too flowable (HFT 24.0 cm)

Following the adjustment of consistency for the reinforcement layer, the selection of an appropriate support layer becomes crucial. Instead of using a tightly knitted textile (as depicted in Figure 3), a coarser textile with the largest feasible mesh size is preferred to optimize material usage and promote sustainability. In this investigation, carbon grid was employed, but in practical applications, the use of lower-performance yet more cost-effective materials like glass or basalt rovings should be considered.

As an illustration, Figure 4 presents an experiment utilizing a textile with a mesh size of 7 x 7 mm. Unlike the optimization conducted for the reinforcement layer, the adjustment was made not to the consistency of the concrete but to the amount of concrete applied. To achieve this, a constant pump delivery rate was maintained while the printing speed was incrementally decreased from fast to slow. Consequently, the quantity of concrete applied increased accordingly. Through visual evaluation of

the test print, the necessary relationship between printing speed and pump delivery rate was determined for the previously found correct viscosity.

Figure 4 also presents a cross-section from a printing trial. In this experiment, detailed images of the bond zone between the roving and concrete were captured using a light microscope at a scale of 100 μm . From left to right, the nozzle velocity was continuously reduced while maintaining a constant pump speed, which corresponds to a constant volumetric flow rate. The red frame indicates that the roving of the textile is already being surrounded by the concrete, but there is still some “splash shadow”. The amount of applied concrete was not sufficient to fully enclose the textile. Within the green frame, the roving is cleanly and completely enclosed, indicating that the correct settings for printing in the textile were found.

Figure 4: Printing trial with constant volumetric flow rate and decreasing of the nozzle velocity.

PROOF OF CONCEPT

Once the correct parameters were determined, larger elements were printed to test their mechanical performance. It is advisable to print flat plates for this purpose, even though curved shapes with a shell-like load-bearing structure should be produced later to ensure rigidity. The textile was initially stretched horizontally and printed with concrete using an industrial six-axis robot and a nozzle with a diameter of 19 mm. The distance between the free suspended support textile and the actual reinforcing layer was 10 mm. The final printing thickness was 20 mm in one printing layer, ensuring that the support textile was not penetrated during the printing process.

In Figure 5a, three prepared variations of support and reinforcement layer, as well as the utilized nozzle, are shown. Figure 5b illustrates the printing process. Due to the complexity involved in producing 3D spacer fabrics, both layers of the textile were initially connected using plastic spacer clips until the optimal settings for the textile were determined.

Figure 5: a) setup for printing with robot, nozzle and stretched textile b) printing of specimens for uniaxial tension tests and pull-off adhesion test

Up to four samples, measuring 20 x 100 x 700 mm³, can be cut from a printed plate for uniaxial tensile test once the concrete has hardened. To ensure uniform stress distribution during clamping in the testing machine, the ends of the samples were ground smooth 180 mm from the edges. The tests were conducted using a universal testing machine, specifically the Instron 8501, with a testing speed of 1 mm/min. Figure 6a showcases a specimen in the testing apparatus. In order to capture deformation and crack formation, a stochastic pattern was sprayed onto the top surface of the samples, and measurements were taken using a GOM ARAMIS measurement system. However, due to interference from the support textile, measurements were only taken on the top surface of the samples.

After testing, in the undamaged clamping regions of the tested specimens, bond pull-off tests according to the DIN EN ISO 4624 standard were conducted to assess the bond between the textile and the concrete. As most failures with high tension occurred in the first mm of concrete, further tests were carried out on samples notched down to the reinforcement level. This was done to induce failure behind the textile, where potential splatter areas could be located. Figure 6b displays the subsequent bond pull-off test in the clamping region.

Figure 6: a) test setup for uniaxial tension test b) test setup for adhesive pull-off test

The mechanical investigations and analysis are still ongoing and have not been concluded. Due to the extensive range of test findings resulting from numerous variations of textile combinations, presenting the results within the scope of this work would be impractical. Therefore, the findings will be presented in another publication or forum where the comprehensive results can be adequately addressed.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, a novel approach to combine the highly topical research areas of additive manufacturing of concrete and textile reinforced concrete is proposed and analysed. By utilizing a multi-layered textile, it is possible to additively manufacture horizontal concrete elements, using the textile as internal reinforcement and integrated formwork at the same time. Suitable textile structures based on warp-knitted non-crimp fabrics are identified and an adjusted concrete mixture is designed. Initial manufacturing trials prove the viability of the approach.

While the experiments presented in this paper demonstrate the overall feasibility of the proposed approach, further investigations are required to understand the interactions between various factors. These factors include variations in textile design (such as material type, mesh opening, layer connection method, etc.), variations in concrete mixture (viscosity, grain size, strength, setting behaviour, etc.), and parameters related to the printing process (pumping volume, nozzle speed and distance, etc.).

It is important to note that the initial printing tests discussed in this paper were conducted on flat geometries. Furthermore, although mechanical tests were performed on the fabricated elements, the results were not evaluated in detail. Evaluation of these mechanical tests is necessary to determine the limitations of this approach for design purposes.

Moreover, additional investigations are needed to explore the production of curved geometries, as depicted in Figure 7. These investigations are essential to unlock the full potential of this innovative production approach.

Figure 7: Examples of curved geometries for future trials

REFERENCES

- Beckmann, B., Bielak, J., Bosbach, S., Scheerer, S., Schmidt, C., Hegger, J., & Curbach, M. (2021). Collaborative research on carbon reinforced concrete structures in the CRC / TRR 280 project. *Civil Engineering Design*, 3(3), 99–109. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cend.202100017>
- Buswell, R., Blanco, A., Cavalaro, S., & Kinnell, P. (Eds.). (2022). *RILEM Bookseries: Volume 37. Third RILEM International Conference on Concrete and Digital Fabrication: Digital Concrete 2022*. Springer.
- Friese, D., Scheurer, M., Hahn, L., Gries, T., & Cherif, C. (2022). Textile reinforcement structures for concrete construction applications—a review. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 56(26), 4041–4064. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219983221127181>
- Gries, T., Bettermann, I., Blaurock, C., Bündgens, A., Dittel, G., Emonts, C., Gesché, V., Glimpel, N., Kolloch, M., Grigat, N., Löcken, H., Löwen, A., Jacobsen, J.-L., Kimm, M., Kelbel, H., Kröger, H., Kuo, K.-C., Peiner, C., Sackmann, J., & Schwab, M. (2022). Aachen Technology

- Overview of 3D Textile Materials and Recent Innovation and Applications. *Applied Composite Materials*, 29(1), 43–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10443-022-10011-w>
- Mechtcherine, V., Dreßler, I., Empelmann, M., Gehlen, C., Glock, C., Kuhn, A., Lanwer, J. P., Lowke, D., Müller, S., Neef, T., Nerella, V. N., Stephan, D., Vasilic, K., Weger, D., & Wiens, U. (2021). Digitaler Betonbau durch additive Verfahren – Sachstand und Forschungsbedarf. *Beton- Und Stahlbetonbau*, 116(11), 881–900. <https://doi.org/10.1002/best.202100067>
- Mechtcherine, V., Michel, A., Liebscher, M., Schneider, K., & Großmann, C. (2020). Mineral-impregnated carbon fiber composites as novel reinforcement for concrete construction: Material and automation perspectives. *Automation in Construction*, 110, 103002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.103002>
- Neef, T., Butler, M., & Mechtcherine, V. (2022). Integrating MINERAL-BONDED CARBON FIBERS INTO 3D CONCRETE PRINTING. In S. Stokkeland (Ed.), *fib proceedings: no. 59. Concrete innovation for sustainability: Proceedings for the 6th fib International Congress 2022 : Held in Oslo, Norway, June 12-16, 2022* (pp. 604–613). International Federation for Structural Concrete.
- Neef, T., Müller, S., & Mechtcherine, V. (2022). Integration of Mineral Impregnated Carbon Fibre (MCF) into Fine 3D-Printed Concrete Filaments. In R. Buswell, A. Blanco, S. Cavalaro, & P. Kinnell (Eds.), *Springer eBook Collection: Vol. 37. Third RILEM International Conference on Concrete and Digital Fabrication: Digital Concrete 2022* (1st ed., Vol. 37, pp. 397–403). Springer International Publishing; Imprint Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-06116-5_59
- Osman-Letelier, J. P., Hückler, A., & Schlaich, M. (2021). Dünnwandige Fertigteile aus vorgespanntem Carbonbeton. *Beton- Und Stahlbetonbau*, 116(10), 786–797. <https://doi.org/10.1002/BEST.202100019>
- Popescu, M., Rippmann, M., Liew, A., Reiter, L., Flatt, R. J., van Mele, T., & Block, P. (2021). Structural design, digital fabrication and construction of the cable-net and knitted formwork of the KnitCandela concrete shell. *Structures*, 31, 1287–1299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2020.02.013>
- Schneider, K., Michel, A., Liebscher, M., Terreri, L., Hempel, S., & Mechtcherine, V. (2019). Mineral-impregnated carbon fibre reinforcement for high temperature resistance of thin-walled concrete structures. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 97, 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2018.12.006>
- Veenendaal, D., West, M., & Block, P. (2011). History and overview of fabric formwork: using fabrics for concrete casting. *Structural Concrete*, 12(3), 164–177. <https://doi.org/10.1002/suco.201100014>
- Walther, T., Schladitz, F., & Curbach, M. (2014). Textilbetonherstellung im Gießverfahren mit Hilfe von Abstandhaltern. *Beton- Und Stahlbetonbau*, 109(3), 216–222. <https://doi.org/10.1002/best.201300080>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation)–SFB/TRR 280. Project-ID: 417002380.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.